

Volume Information Entropy and Classical Mechanics Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 8, 2025

In the statistical mechanics of an ideal gas, a uniform distribution is used for volume if a potential is not present, i.e. $p(x,y,z) = 1/V$. This result is often presented in terms of the maximization of the number of possible states. If a volume is broken into N tiny cells, then a particle has equal probability to be any of these, hence maximizing uncertainty. More formally, the maximization of $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ subject to $\sum_i p(i) = 1$ gives the same distribution.

In Part I, we argued that in the volume case, one does not need to think in terms of maximum entropy or states, but may obtain the same result by considering the removal of time from Newtonian mechanics. In particular, we considered the deterministic case of two particles in two 1-D boxes of lengths L and $2L$. Each starts at $x=0, t=0$ and moves with v . If one removes time, then one may choose a position x in L and consider all possible times which map to it. This set of times will map to 2 distinct x values in $2L$, 3 distinct x values in $3L$ etc. In other words, this is deterministic motion, but the lack of information yields a probability proportional to $1/V$.

Here, we consider another deterministic way of obtaining this same result. We consider that a bound particle in a 1-D container of length L moves with a constant speed. This means that it spends the same amount of time dt in each dx . This amount depends on the speed, but that drops out with normalization of $P(x) dx = dx/L$. Thus, $1/L$ or $1/V$ appears again for a completely deterministic problem and no consideration of states is needed. We argue that in an ideal gas with no potential, if a particle is not colliding, it is moving with a constant speed. Given that the speed is not tied to x , on average (v_{rms} for example) the particle should have the same speed at each x . Thus, in terms of an average speed, the particle spends that same amount of time dt in each dx and so one should have $P(x)dx = dx/L$, i.e. $1/V$ is the probability to use based on deterministic considerations and not on the idea of maximizing entropy or considering cells in a volume, we argue. (Note: Mathematically, there is nothing wrong with maximization or entropy or cells, but we argue that one should try to see statistical mechanics emerge from Newtonian mechanics and this involves viewing dynamic motion.)

We finally consider the situation of $P(x)dx = C dx/v(x)$ where $\frac{1}{2}m v(x)^2 + V(x) = E$ for a potential. This is a deterministic Newtonian nonrelativistic bound scenario and does not yield the statistical $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. We try to show that this is because in addition to volume considerations, there are energy considerations and $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ is linked with those. In fact, the $V(x)$ in $\exp(-(E + V(x))/T)$ follows from the existence of deterministic Newtonian motion through the potential.

Statistical Mechanics and Maximization of Entropy

Statistical mechanics seems to be presented in terms of the maximization of the number of states subject to constraints. In other words, one thinks of states and not dynamical motion. We argue, however, that dynamical motion is physical and there is no reason why one should not base statistical statements on it or its average instead of postulating minimum information by maximizing configurations with respect to constraints. It is not that this is wrong, but we argue

that one may perhaps see the emergence of the statistical situation more clearly in the latter approach. In particular, in Part I, we argued that the well known:

$$P(x,y,z) dx dy dz = dx dy dz / V \quad ((1))$$

, which follows from maximizing $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ subject to $\sum_i p(i) = 1$, or from cell considerations and minimal information, also follows from deterministic motion.

In Part I, we considered two 1-D boxes of lengths L and $2L$. A particle starts at $x=0$, $t=0$ in each and moves with speed v . This is a completely deterministic scenario. We then suggested removing the clock so all time information is gone. One then does not know where the particles are, but the motion is still deterministic. In Part I, we showed that if one assumes an x position in the L box, one may list all possible times associated with this position. If one applies these specific times to the $2L$ box, one finds that they map into two distinct x points with equal probability, 3 for a $3L$ box etc. In other words, if there is a probability p to be at x in the L box, then given that x is one of the two points in the $2L$ box, there is a $.5p$ probability for the particle to be at x in the $2L$ box. This is the same result as maximizing entropy or considering states and minimum information, but is based on completely deterministic motion with information removed.

Thus, in the volume case, the $1/V$ probability result may be understood in terms of dynamical motion of a single particle.

A Second Deterministic Approach to Volume Probability

A simpler approach, which also makes use of deterministic motion, is the following. If one has a particle moving at constant speed in a 1-D box of size L , then the amount of time spent in each dx is the same, namely dt given by $dx = v dt$, so:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is sometimes used to show that a quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, becomes $1/L$ when one writes: $1/\sqrt{L} \cdot 1/\sqrt{L} \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. We argue here that it has relevance for an ideal gas. Even though the motion is entirely deterministic, $1/L$ or $1/V$ appears as the probability.

We note that in an ideal gas, if a particle is not colliding with another or the walls, it is moving with a constant speed. The problem is that it may have different speeds, meaning that dt for a fixed dx at x is different for each. On average, however, v_{rms} should be the same at each x if there is no potential present. In such a case, using v_{rms} in a deterministic manner:

$$Dx = v_{rms} dt \quad ((3))$$

One has the same dt for each x point and so should have a uniform distribution in position, even for a completely deterministic problem. We argue that this description is closer to the physical picture than the idea of states and minimal information which is purely statistical and does not make a direct link to the deterministic Newtonian mechanics present.

The Case of a Potential

For an ideal gas, if a potential $V(x)$ is present, then the spatial probability is:

$$P(x) = \exp(-V(x)/T) \quad ((4))$$

On the other hand, a particle moving in a bound state would have a probability based on dx of:

$$P(x)dx = Cdx / v(x) \text{ where } .5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

((4)) and ((5)) are not equivalent. We note that for a statistical gas (ideal gas), there is more than simply volume probability. The particles collide with each other such that energy is conserved. This means that:

$$p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ for } V(x_0)=0 \quad ((6)) \quad \text{This leads to: } p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((7))$$

If a potential exists, then $e_i + V(x_0) (=0) = e_i' + V(x)$. Thus, ((7)) becomes:

$$C_2 \exp(-(e_i' + V(x))/T) \quad ((8))$$

In other words, there is still Newtonian deterministic motion when the particle is not colliding, but this time it is through a potential $V(x)$. Thus, an ideal gas is still very Newtonian. In fact, we have argued in previous notes that one essentially has a Newtonian picture and removes information about some variables, e.g. time and variables linked to collisions. This leaves position and e_i as variables, together with constraints which are consistent with Newtonian mechanics, namely for no potential, dt is the same for each dx based on a constant v_{rms} so $1/V$ is the position probability and collisions conserve energy so one has $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for no $V(x)$ and $\exp(-(e_i' + V(x))/T)$ for $V(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in Part I that using $1/V$ as position probability does not need to follow from maximization of entropy or from minimizing state information. It may follow from Newtonian deterministic analysis with some information removed, i.e. time. In other words, the probability which results must be consistent with Newtonian mechanics.

Here we present a second example of deterministic motion leading to $1/V$ as position probability. We note that for a constant speed $dx=v dt$, so dt is the same for each dx . This leads to $P(x)dx = dx/L$ even for deterministic motion. In an ideal gas, we argue that one may $dx = v_{rms} dt$ and so should expect $1/V$ as the position probability. This argument is based strictly on deterministic motion. We note that in the case of a potential $V(x)$, the energy probability $\exp(-e_i/T)$ becomes $\exp(-(e_i + V(x))/T)$, but that there is still deterministic Newtonian motion when the particle is not colliding, but this time it is through a potential.